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The contribution of participatory decision making in the planning of ecosystem-based adaptation

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Inland and coastal floods are becoming more frequent and severe, affecting natural and socioeconomic systems. Coastal urban areas, where population and economic activity are highly concentrated, appear as particularly vulnerable to these events. Local adaptation to climate change benefits from the integration of opinions from different stakeholders in the design and decision process, helping practitioners, planners, and policy makers to address climate change. This process can be operated under the umbrella of Living Labs, where innovative solutions to specific problems can be defined, designed and created through a social-iterative approach. Multicriteria analysis (MCA) is a suitable decision-making tool to develop within the context of Living Labs and climate change adaptation as it allows to capture perceptions from different actors about adaptation measures characterised through various criteria. This study presents the results of an MCA applied to the evaluation of Ecosystem-based Adaptation (EbA) to flooding in three Coastal City Living Labs of the Iberian Peninsula: An ex-ante analysis in Vilanova i la Geltrú (Spain) focused on potential measures to be implemented in an intermittent river-stream; Benidorm (Spain) followed an interim evaluation of planned EbA to address flooding in different city areas; and an ex-post analysis was performed in Oeiras (Metropolitan area of Lisbon; Portugal) to assess the perception of different stakeholders about the performance of already implemented measures along a river stream.